

Wide Artificial Intelligence is here

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is traditionally classified into three main categories: Artificial Narrow Intelligence (ANI), Artificial General Intelligence (AGI), and Artificial Super Intelligence (ASI). While this classification has been useful, it no longer fully reflects the current achievements in AI. Modern systems, such as generative language models and multimodal AI, surpass the capabilities of ANI but do not meet the requirements of AGI, such as self-awareness and the ability to generalize knowledge. These systems, which integrate various functions, call for a new terminological approach. This article proposes the introduction of the term Wide Artificial Intelligence (WAI) to describe systems that integrate diverse capabilities and represent a transitional stage between ANI and AGI. Recognizing and defining this level of AI development is crucial for better understanding the current state of technology and its societal impact. The concept of WAI arises from my research on the social and technological consequences of AI development and represents an innovative attempt to address an existing terminological and research gap. WAI not only specifies a new category of systems but also enables a deeper understanding of the evolving dynamics of human-technology relationships.

Keywords: Wide artificial intelligence, generative AI, artificial intelligence classification, human-machine interaction, sociological impacts of AI.

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) is not just a technological revolution; it also marks an intellectual breakthrough that is reshaping the prevailing paradigm of social life. It is a field that will inevitably shape the future of human civilization, influencing every aspect of our lives. The changes initiated by the advancement of digital technologies—especially with the widespread

accessibility of generative AI two years ago—are so profound that their full implications remain difficult to predict. We can only attempt to imagine their scope, though it is likely that AI itself will define the limits of its capabilities and open new avenues for development in the near future.

Generative artificial intelligence is redefining this technology by mimicking the human mind's abilities across various areas of activity. Modern AI models understand conversational context, communicate in natural language, recognize patterns and structures, solve problems, make decisions, and carry out tasks traditionally requiring human intellect. AI is currently defined as a multidisciplinary field of engineering. As both a technology and a scientific research area, it encompasses computer science, neurocognitive science, biology, neuropsychology, systems and organizational theories, and the social sciences. AI systems are capable of creating models of intelligent behavior and programs that not only simulate such behavior but also replicate it (Przegalińska, 2020).

Understanding the consequences of AI development has become one of the central challenges of contemporary sociology. The birth of sociology coincided with an era in which the effects of the Industrial Revolution profoundly impacted societies. Auguste Comte, regarded as the father of sociology, recognized the urgent need for a science that could explain rapid technological changes and offer solutions to emerging social problems. Similarly, today, sociology and other social sciences play a crucial role in understanding the AI revolution, which in the coming decades will transform social structures and human relationships. The emerging world requires a new vocabulary, and interpreting it will be essential for understanding the new forms of interaction.

The development of AI demands an interdisciplinary research approach that bridges technical and humanistic sciences. AI sociology is emerging as a key tool to better understand how this technology impacts social structures and relationships, as well as human-machine interactions. In this context, creating new categories and terms to accurately describe the current stage of AI development becomes crucial.

Currently, AI is most commonly classified into three categories: Artificial Narrow Intelligence (ANI), Artificial General Intelligence (AGI), and Artificial Super Intelligence (ASI). However, modern systems, such as generative language models and multimodal AI, surpass the capabilities of ANI (Russell & Norvig, 2021; IBM, 2024), while falling short of the requirements of AGI (Goertzel, 2014; IBM, 2024) or ASI (Kurzweil, 2005; Bostrom, 2014). These systems, with their ability to combine various functionalities and operate across a broad range of applications, demand a new terminological approach. Therefore, I propose introducing the term **Wide Artificial Intelligence (WAI)** to highlight the unique characteristics of contemporary AI systems and address the research gap in the classification of this technology.

Theoretical context

Identifying a research gap in AI classification

The rapid development of generative artificial intelligence in 2022 challenged the classical division of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into Artificial Narrow Intelligence (ANI), Artificial General Intelligence (AGI), and Artificial Super Intelligence (ASI), which had effectively described the evolution of this technology for years. Contemporary AI systems exhibit characteristics that transcend the traditional boundaries of ANI while not yet achieving the capabilities of AGI or ASI. The concept of Wide Artificial Intelligence (WAI) offers a solution to this gap. This article presents arguments supporting the redefinition of AI categories and highlights the significance of a new classification for further research on technology and its societal implications.

Artificial Narrow Intelligence (ANI) has been the most widely used form of AI for many years, referring to systems designed and trained to perform specific tasks (Russell & Norvig, 2021; IBM, 2024; Nilsson, 2010). Its roots date back to the early days of artificial intelligence as a discipline when researchers such as John McCarthy and Allen Newell focused on creating algorithms capable of solving specific problems, such as playing chess or proving mathematical theorems. In the 1960s and 1970s, the first ANI systems, such as the ELIZA program, demonstrated the ability to simulate natural language conversations. ELIZA, created by Joseph Weizenbaum, was one of the first chatbots enabling real-time interaction. However, its responses were based not on advanced semantic analysis but rather on simple pattern-matching techniques (Weizenbaum, 1966).

Artificial Narrow Intelligence focuses on narrowly defined tasks. Despite lacking the ability to perform comprehensive and complex actions beyond its intended domain, it is characterized by exceptional efficiency and precision in its applications. Examples of ANI include voice assistants like Amazon's Alexa (Amazon, 2024) and Apple's Siri (Apple, 2024), which use natural language processing to interact with users. Another example is recommendation systems used on streaming platforms such as Netflix (Netflix, 2024), Amazon Prime (Amazon Prime Video, 2024), and Spotify (Spotify, 2024), which analyze user preferences to suggest personalized content. ANI is also utilized in autonomous vehicles, which integrate various technologies to navigate safely in the real world (Tesla, 2024). These systems process data from sensors, cameras, and radars in real-time, enabling obstacle avoidance and predicting the behavior of other road users.

Another common application of ANI is virtual assistants managing customer service chats on websites (Zendesk, 2024), automating customer service processes by answering basic questions or directing users to the appropriate departments. Everyday applications of ANI, often unnoticed as AI, include email classification systems that effectively separate unwanted messages from desired ones. Similarly, fraud prevention mechanisms in online banking analyze user behavior and detect potentially suspicious transactions, preventing fraud.

General Artificial Intelligence (AGI), also known as strong artificial intelligence (Strong AI, Russell & Norvig, 2021), represents the concept of a system possessing human-level intelligence. Such a system would be capable of performing any intellectual task that a human can, including problem-solving based on generalized knowledge, learning, and planning for the future. Unlike narrow artificial intelligence (ANI), AGI would possess self-awareness and the ability to understand and adapt to new situations in a universal manner, unrestricted by predefined tasks. Currently, AGI remains theoretical, although organizations like OpenAI and IBM are actively conducting research aimed at developing this technology (OpenAI, 2024; IBM, 2024). These efforts focus on building systems capable of generalizing knowledge and making decisions in ways reminiscent of human intelligence. Ray Kurzweil, in his works, predicts that AGI could be achieved by the mid-21st century, ushering humanity into a new technological era known as the singularity (Kurzweil, 2005). Achieving AGI would pose significant

technological, ethical, and societal challenges, including questions about controlling such a system and its potential impact on human life.

Artificial Superintelligence (ASI), or superintelligence, refers to a concept of strong artificial intelligence that surpasses the capabilities of the human brain in all fields, including creativity, cognitive abilities, and social skills. ASI could not only perform tasks at a level higher than the most capable humans but also predict, analyze, and solve problems beyond human capacity. Although superintelligence remains speculative and is often portrayed in science fiction, it is a significant topic for AI researchers due to its potential consequences. The development of ASI could revolutionize social, economic, and technological life while also presenting serious risks, such as loss of control over systems exceeding human capabilities. Discussions about ASI focus on its long-term impact, particularly in the context of existential risks to humanity (Bostrom, 2014; Kurzweil, 2005). Ray Kurzweil argues that the question of achieving ASI is not "if it will happen" but rather "when it will happen," predicting that humanity will face this challenge by the mid-21st century (Kurzweil, 2005). Similar predictions are shared by other researchers, who highlight the rapid development of AI and the scalability of existing technologies (Tegmark, 2017). Research on ASI encompasses both technological development paths and ethical implications and safety strategies. The Future of Humanity Institute at Oxford, led by Nick Bostrom, investigates potential scenarios for ASI development and methods to mitigate risks associated with losing control over superintelligent systems (Bostrom, 2014).

Another crucial aspect is the role of contemporary AI systems in laying the groundwork for ASI development. Generative models, such as GPT-4, and technologies like deep learning and neural networks provide foundational tools that can be scaled toward more advanced forms of intelligence (Russell & Norvig, 2021). IBM and OpenAI are also involved in research on AGI and ASI, focusing on safety and responsible technological development (IBM, 2024; OpenAI, 2024). In the social and ethical context, discussions about ASI include questions about whether superintelligence can coexist with humans, how to ensure its goals align with human values, and what legal regulations will be necessary in the post-ASI era. Tegmark (2017) emphasizes that a key challenge is creating frameworks that allow superintelligence to be integrated in a way that is safe and beneficial for humanity.

Limitations of current AI classification

The need for a new category

The prevailing classification of artificial intelligence, based on the division into ANI, AGI, and ASI, has become insufficient in light of the rapid development of generative AI. Contemporary models, such as GPT-4 (OpenAI, 2024) and DALL-E (OpenAI, 2024), exceed the traditional boundaries of narrow artificial intelligence (ANI). These systems not only perform specific tasks with high precision but also enable the creation of multimodal ecosystems, where various technologies work together to generate complex responses and solutions. Moreover, these systems can understand the context of extensive dialogues, process complex commands, and integrate various capabilities, such as generating text, images, and sound (Google AI, 2024; ElevenLabs, 2024).

While modern AI models do not yet meet the criteria for Artificial General Intelligence (AGI), such as self-awareness or the ability to generalize knowledge, they clearly surpass the capabilities of conventionally defined ANI. Models like AlphaCode (DeepMind, 2024), which support programming, and Meta's LLaMA (Meta AI, 2024), demonstrate that AI can exhibit advanced skills in specific domains while simultaneously integrating diverse functions within a single system. Similarly, Anthropic's Claude (Anthropic, 2024) focuses on safer interactions, addressing user needs in a contextual and flexible manner.

The lack of an appropriate category to describe this new level of advancement hinders both scientific research and practical applications of AI technology. The terminological gap is particularly evident in the context of generative AI models, which combine various functions within a unified structure but do not fit within the boundaries of existing definitions of narrow artificial intelligence.

Thus, there is a pressing need for a new category to fill this research and terminological void. The proposed concept of Wide Artificial Intelligence (WAI) represents an attempt to address this issue by defining a new stage in the development of artificial intelligence. WAI encompasses systems that integrate diverse functions and capabilities within a single model, not yet meeting the criteria for AGI but surpassing the traditional scope of ANI.

Introducing the WAI category not only enables a better understanding of the current level of AI advancement but also lays the groundwork for further research into the social and technological implications of this multidimensional technology. The next section of the article will present a detailed analysis of the WAI concept, its definition, and examples of contemporary systems that may fall under this classification.

Proposal for a new category in AI classification

Wide Artificial Intelligence

In recent years, narrow artificial intelligence (ANI) has evolved significantly due to advancements in natural language processing architectures, particularly transformers, which have become the foundation for generative AI models. With progress in machine learning technologies, especially deep learning and the development of complex neural networks, ANI now facilitates the creation of systems capable of generating content across various domains, including images, videos, sounds, text, and real-time contextual conversations with chatbots. This progress has transcended the boundaries of classical ANI, enabling the emergence of more advanced AI models and highlighting the urgent need for a new classification category to better reflect the current state of technology.

Over seventy years ago, Alan Turing addressed the question of creating thinking machines in his groundbreaking paper *Computing Machinery and Intelligence* (Turing, 1950). He proposed the procedure now widely known as the Turing Test, initially called the Imitation Game, as an objective and practical criterion to evaluate a machine's ability to imitate human thinking. According to Turing, if a machine engaged in the Imitation Game could achieve a level where human judges correctly identify whether they are conversing with a machine or a human only 70% of the time, it could be deemed "thinking" by his criteria. In other words, the machine would pass the test if it managed to mislead judges in at least 30% of cases.

According to a study published in May 2024 by the University of California, San Diego, OpenAI's GPT-4 model was recognized as a "thinking machine" and successfully passed the Turing Test (Jones & Bergen, 2024). The test aimed to determine whether the machine could engage in a conversation indistinguishable from that of a human. The experiment involved

500 participants who engaged in five-minute conversations with four different interlocutors: a human, the ELIZA chatbot from 1966, the GPT-3.5 model, and GPT-4. After each conversation, participants were asked to identify whether their conversational partner was a human or a machine.

The results revealed that ELIZA was identified as human by 22% of participants, GPT-3.5 by 50%, and GPT-4 by 54%. In comparison, the human participant was correctly identified as human by 67% of respondents. The researchers noted that GPT-4's ability to surpass the 50% threshold of misleading participants suggests it is nearing the ability to pass the Turing Test, although it has not yet achieved full success in this regard. Importantly, while Turing's original Imitation Game criteria considered a 30% success rate sufficient to qualify a machine as "thinking," contemporary expectations for AI have significantly increased. This reflects stricter standards and greater societal awareness of AI's capabilities and potential implications.

The success of GPT-4 in the Turing Test demonstrates that it has surpassed the functional boundaries traditionally defined for ANI models, marking a breakthrough in the understanding of AI's capabilities. This achievement represents not only significant technological progress but also opens new avenues for research that demand further exploration. The results of the Turing Test confirm that modern generative AI models have exceeded the scope of narrow AI and are progressing toward AGI. However, the current operational space occupied by these advanced AI models remains insufficiently defined, and a terminological and research gap persists. Therefore, introducing the classification term *Wide Artificial Intelligence* (WAI) becomes essential.

Wide Artificial Intelligence (WAI) represents a new stage in AI development that surpasses the capabilities of narrow AI (ANI) while not yet achieving the attributes characteristic of general AI (AGI). WAI is distinguished by its ability to perform diverse tasks across a broader range than ANI, such as generating text, images, sounds, and videos or conducting context-aware conversations with humans. These systems integrate advanced and complex functionalities, enabling the combination of various skills within a cohesive system. These capabilities indicate that generative AI models have surpassed the boundaries defined by classical ANI, opening new possibilities for research on artificial intelligence and its applications. The next section

will delve into a detailed analysis of the WAI concept, its definition, and examples of contemporary systems that fit into this category.

Wide Artificial Intelligence

A new stage in AI development

Wide Artificial Intelligence (WAI) represents a new stage in AI development that surpasses the capabilities of narrow AI (ANI) while not yet achieving the distinctive features of artificial general intelligence (AGI). WAI is characterized by its ability to perform a variety of tasks across a broader spectrum than ANI, including generating text, images, audio, videos, and engaging in context-aware conversations with humans. These systems combine advanced and complex functionalities, enabling the integration of various skills into a single, cohesive system. These capabilities demonstrate that generative AI models have surpassed the boundaries defined by classical ANI, opening new possibilities for research into artificial intelligence and its applications.

Examples of Wide Artificial Intelligence (WAI) include contemporary systems that integrate diverse capabilities across multiple domains and technologies. Generative models such as GPT-4 (OpenAI, 2024) not only answer questions but also produce detailed literary texts, generate computer code, and analyze complex data. These functions, which were previously the domain of narrowly specialized ANI systems, have been integrated into a single cohesive model, marking a breakthrough in practical AI applications.

Another example of WAI is multimodal systems such as DALL-E and Midjourney, which combine text comprehension capabilities with image generation (OpenAI, 2024; Midjourney, 2024). These technologies find applications in graphic design, marketing, and social media, enabling the creation of personalized visual content based on textual descriptions. WAI bridges the gap between language and visualization, representing a step forward in the complexity of AI applications.

Advanced conversational systems like ChatGPT, Google Gemini, and Claude represent another facet of WAI (OpenAI, 2024; Google, 2024; Anthropic, 2024). In addition to engaging in conversations, they can translate languages, answer questions on complex scientific topics, and generate creative ideas. These systems are used in customer service, voice assistants, and even as support in therapeutic processes. Their ability to understand context and adapt flexibly in conversations surpasses the capabilities of traditional chatbots based on ANI.

WAI also encompasses systems that integrate data from various sources to support decision-making. Examples include advanced city management systems (smart cities) that analyze data from cameras, traffic sensors, and weather systems to optimize public transportation, manage energy, and improve citizen safety (IBM, 2024). In these applications, WAI combines analytical capabilities with elements of automation and real-time decision-making.

The examples above illustrate that Wide Artificial Intelligence (WAI) models occupy the space between ANI and AGI, confirming that recognizing and defining this stage in AI development is essential for understanding the current state of technology and its societal impact.

Conclusion

Artificial intelligence (AI) is an interdisciplinary field that has emerged through the integration of various branches of science. Computer science, mathematics, physics, psychology, neurobiology, linguistics, cybernetics, economics, and cognitive science have all played pivotal roles in its development, particularly over the past seventy years, since the publication of Alan Turing's groundbreaking paper and the question he posed: *Can machines think?* The further advancement of this technology will inevitably require the collaboration of technical, natural, and increasingly, social sciences. The changes brought about by AI, particularly in the social domain, will demand that social sciences, especially sociology, focus on analyzing its consequences, diagnosing challenges, and explaining how this technology will impact our civilization. Equally crucial will be the search for solutions to social problems that may arise as a result of its implementation.

One might speculate that even Turing could not have foreseen how his concept would ignite the imagination of scientists on such a scale, ultimately manifesting in the form of generative artificial intelligence. Turing became the architect of one of humanity's greatest inventions—AI. Yet it is difficult to assume he could have fully envisioned the potential of thinking machines and their impact on the future of humankind. Similarly, it remains challenging to predict what AI will bring to humanity in the years to come.

Bibliography

1. Bostrom, N. (2014). *Superintelligence: Paths, Dangers, Strategies*. Oxford University Press.
2. Goertzel, B. (2014). *Artificial General Intelligence: Concept, State of the Art, and Future Prospects*. Paris: Atlantis Press.
3. Kurzweil, R. (2005). *The Singularity Is Near: When Humans Transcend Biology*. Viking Penguin, a member of Penguin Group (USA) Inc.
4. Nilsson, N. (2010). *The Quest for Artificial Intelligence: A History of Ideas and Achievements*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK. ISBN: 9780521122931.
5. Przegalińska, A. (2020). *Artificial Intelligence. Non-human, Superhuman*. ZNAK Publishing House, Kraków.
6. Russell, S. & Norvig, P. (2021). *Artificial Intelligence: A Modern Approach*. 4th Edition. Pearson Education, Inc., Publishing as Pearson.
7. Tegmark, M. (2017). *Life 3.0: Being Human in the Age of Artificial Intelligence*. New York: Alfred A. Knopf.
8. Weizenbaum, J. (1966). ELIZA - A Computer Program For the Study of Natural Language Communication Between Man and Machine. *Communications of the ACM*, 9(1), pp. 36-45. DOI: 10.1145/365153.365168.

Online Sources

1. Amazon (2024). *What is Alexa?* [online] Available at: <https://developer.amazon.com/en-US/alexa> [Accessed 24 Nov. 2024].
2. Amazon Prime Video (2024). *Prime Video Recommendations*. [online] Available at: <https://www.primevideo.com> [Accessed 24 Nov. 2024].

3. Anthropic (2024). *Claude: Safer Conversational AI*. [online] Available at: <https://www.anthropic.com/claude> [Accessed 24 Nov. 2024].
4. Apple (2024). *Siri – Your Intelligent Assistant*. [online] Available at: <https://www.apple.com/siri> [Accessed 24 Nov. 2024].
5. DeepMind (2024). *AlphaCode: AI for Programming*. [online] Available at: <https://deepmind.google/discover/blog/competitive-programming-with-alphacode> [Accessed 24 Nov. 2024].
6. ElevenLabs (2024). *High-Quality Voice Generation*. [online] Available at: <https://www.elevenlabs.io> [Accessed 24 Nov. 2024].
7. Google AI (2024). *Gemini: Advanced Conversational AI*. [online] Available at: <https://gemini.google.com/?hl=pl> [Accessed 24 Nov. 2024].
8. IBM (2024). *Artificial Intelligence: Current Trends and Classifications*. [online] Available at: <https://www.ibm.com/topics/artificial-intelligence> [Accessed 24 Nov. 2024].
9. Midjourney (2024). *AI for Creative Visual Content*. [online] Available at: <https://www.midjourney.com> [Accessed 24 Nov. 2024].
10. Netflix (2024). *How Netflix Recommends Movies and TV Shows*. [online] Available at: <https://www.netflix.com/pl/> [Accessed 24 Nov. 2024].
11. OpenAI (2024). *ChatGPT: Advanced Conversational AI*. [online] Available at: <https://www.openai.com> [Accessed 24 Nov. 2024].
12. OpenAI (2024). *DALL-E*. [online] Available at: <https://www.openai.com/dall-e> [Accessed 24 Nov. 2024].
13. Spotify (2024). *How Spotify Personalizes Playlists*. [online] Available at: <https://open.spotify.com> [Accessed 24 Nov. 2024].
14. Tesla (2024). *Autopilot and Full Self-Driving Capability*. [online] Available at: <https://www.tesla.com/autopilot> [Accessed 24 Nov. 2024].
15. Zendesk (2024). *AI-Powered Chatbots*. [online] Available at: <https://www.zendesk.com/chatbots> [Accessed 24 Nov. 2024].